

IRIS Software Protocol v1

Revision notes

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Dear Editors,

We express our gratitude for the time and effort dedicated to the reviewing of our submitted manuscript. We appreciate the understanding of the first version of protocol being a very initial draft, and we are thankful for the constructive feedback provided.

We worked diligently to address all the concerns raised by the referees. Below we provide our detailed response to their comments. We hope that the applied revisions are to the satisfaction of the editors.

Kind regards,

Leonardo Zilli, on behalf of the authors

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Reviewer 1 - <https://doi.org/10.32388/LVTB00>

Comment I (Reviewer 1):

A minor issue, caused by the early stage of the protocol, is the absence of any specification about the future storage of the data produced and where and how they will be accessed.

Answer: The focus of our research is a study of already existing datasets. The production of new data is not within the scope of this research. The data used to achieve the results of this research will nevertheless be stored in a repository accessible to the public. We have added a link to this information in the guidelines of the protocol.

Assignment: Leonardo
Done

Comment II (Reviewer 1):

A first observation that emerges is the absence of any influence of the state of the art and comparison with it while developing the protocol. It would be interesting to understand if any previous work has been used to develop this tool and if not, to describe why.

Answer: No previous work has been used to develop the protocol. The protocol was developed from scratch to address the specific needs of the research. To our knowledge, no similar study exists that tackles our specific issue. This is the reason for the absence of a comparison with the state of the art.

Assignment: Leonardo
Effort not estimated

Comment III (Reviewer 1):

it could be added a section on the interpretation of the results obtained by the “research question answering” section.

Answer: That would be a valuable addition to the protocol. We will include a section on the interpretation of the obtained results in the future.

Assignment: Leonardo
Feasible

Comment IV (Reviewer 1):

In the two Query sections, it could be useful to understand what each query does, to insert a short verbal description defining what each query returns.

Answer: We totally agree, and we will be sure to include detail explanations of the queries once the software is further developed.

Assignment: Leonardo
Feasible

Comment V (Reviewer 1):

The link requirements.txt returns a 404 page.

Answer: We have fixed this, thank you for pointing it out.

Assignment: Leonardo
Done

Comment VI (Reviewer 1):

A link to IRIS and OpenCitations could be inserted in the abstract.

Answer: We decided to omit the links from the abstract to keep it concise. However, we have included the links in the introduction.

Assignment: Leonardo
Effort not estimated

Comment VII (Reviewer 1):

The “Before starting” heading could be replaced with “To run the code.”

Answer: The “Before starting” heading is not something we have written ourselves, but it is automatically generated by protocols.io. We cannot therefore change it.

Assignment: Leonardo
Death

Reviewer 2 - <https://doi.org/10.32388/PSHNEC>

Comment VIII (Reviewer 2):

While reviewing this, I found myself uncertain about the meaning of “the string of the authors.”

Answer: The description of the contents of the IRIS dataset have been extracted directly from the README file written by the authors of the dataset. Indeed, by “string fo the authors” it is indeed meant the string containing the name of the authors of each publication. We acknowledge that it might be expressed more clearly and have now clarified this in the protocol.

Assignment: Leonardo
Done

Comment IX (Reviewer 2):

*Concerning the section detailing the conversion of CSV files into DataFrames *iris_id_df*, *iris_master_df*, and *iris_relation_df* there arises a question: Are only these three DataFrames involved, or are additional files also included?*

Answer: Only some of the CSV files are indeed converted into DataFrames. We have now clarified the process in the protocol.

Assignment: Leonardo
Done

Comment X (Reviewer 2):

The section discussing the use of the OpenCitations Meta Sparql endpoint to obtain CSV files through queries lacks specificity regarding the nature of the queries employed, rendering it difficult to evaluate the resulting files

Answer: This section was written as an embryonic overview of the process. We will include more precise steps as we further develop the software used for the research.

Assignment: Leonardo
Work in progress

Revised version of the manuscript:

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